

DNA mediated electrocatalytic enhancement on α -Fe₂O₃-PEDOT-C-MoS₂ hybrid nanostructures for Riboflavin detection on Screen Printed Electrode

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Abstract

Facile synthesis of iron oxide nanorods and PEDOT(poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene)) nanospheres on carbon supported MoS₂ (C-MoS₂) is reported for riboflavin (RF) sensing. Further, a novel aqueous-based DNA wrapped up with α -Fe₂O₃-PEDOT-C-MoS₂ scaffold shows high electrocatalytic activity compared to that of α -Fe₂O₃-PEDOT-C-MoS₂ composite in biosensing. The α -Fe₂O₃-PEDOT-C-MoS₂/GCE demonstrates the linear response of RF in the concentration range of 800 nM–700 μ M, with detection limit 79 nM (S/N=3 σ /b) whereas α -Fe₂O₃-PEDOT-C-MoS₂-DNA/GCE composite shows a wider range 300 nM–1 mM, with low detection limit 5 nM comparatively. Similarly, α -Fe₂O₃-PEDOT-C-MoS₂-DNA/SPE exhibits still wider range of 100 nM–1 mM, with detection limit 12 nM. Interestingly, it is also observed that the α -Fe₂O₃-PEDOT-C-MoS₂-DNA/GCE reduces the oxidation potential of RF by 30 mV. Thus the excellent behavior of proposed biosensor can be attributed to the unique behavior of DNA in giving wider detection range and good electrocatalytic behavior towards RF. The fabricated sensor exhibited highly sensitive and selective detection of RF. The real sample analysis was also executed in human urine, milk powder and pharmaceutical drug without any preliminary treatment.

